

Maputopias: Cartographies of Communication, Coordination and Action — The cases of Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia

Abstract

Maps have been established as objects bestowed with knowledge, power and impact. In the hands of people, maps have been a form of political counter-power. The emergence of digital cartography, mobile media, data crowdsourcing platforms and geographic information systems strengthens the maps' muscle and coincides with a growing interest in crisis and activist mapping, a practice that blends the capabilities of the geoweb with humanitarian assistance and campaigning. Based on empirical observation, case studies and interviews, this article analyses the emergence of digital cartography as a new paradigm in activism and humanitarianism by examining how two platforms –Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia— use maps. Ushahidi was created in 2008 in Kenya, marking the beginning of *geoactivism*, which employs digital cartography and often crowdsourced data to provide alternative narratives and spaces for communication and action. InfoAmazonia –dedicated to environmental issues and human rights in the Amazon region— was created in 2012. Since then, other geoactivist initiatives proliferated, presenting three different outcomes in the shape of a paradigm shift, several disruptions and criticism. This study examines these consequences, scrutinising how humanitarianism and activism –as fields of power and knowledge— are being reconfigured by new cartographic practices.

Keywords: geoactivism, digital humanitarianism, crisis mapping, critical cartography, data activism, activist mapping

Introduction

'Power comes from the map and it traverses the way maps are made' (Harley 1989: 12).

On January 12, 2010, at 7 pm, a 7.3 magnitude earthquake hit Haiti, followed by more than fifty aftershocks over the next twelve days. More than 220,000 people died, and over 300,000 were injured in the catastrophe (Disasters Emergency Committee 2015). When Patrick Meier, then Director of Crisis Mapping at Ushahidi, heard the news, he contacted the International Network of Crisis Mappers to launch a map visualising tweets and Facebook comments (Norheim-Hagtun & Meier 2010: 81). In three hours, they were already visualising verified reports. And within the first two weeks a text message hotline had been established and hundreds of volunteers from around the world had gathered and mapped 1,500 reports of emergencies and appeals for help (Hesse 2010). More than 3,500 reports were created overall (ibid.).

An independent evaluation of the Haiti deployment (Figure 1) found that it tackled “key information gaps” in the early period of the response before large organisations were operative, providing geolocalised data to small non-governmental organisations (NGOs) that did not have a field presence, offering situational awareness and rapid information with high degree of accuracy, and enabling citizens' decision-making (Morrow et al. 2011: 4).

Figure 1: Ushahidi Haiti Project Map

Source: (Meier 2012).

The basis for the success of the Haiti deployment was that the mapping effort mobilized dozens of members of the Haitian diaspora, who not only translated messages from and into Creole French – since machine translation engines for Haitian Creole were not available at the time—, but also positioned the information on the map (Hesse 2010).

The deployment was flawed, though. Further evaluations concluded that the project lacked the preparation, early partner-building, outreach, training, workflow planning and citizen engagement needed for a crisis map to operate at its maximum capability (Omenya 2013; Morrow et al. 2011).

Ushahidi has also been criticised for being depended on corporate technologies, such as mobile technology, whose business models are based on low production costs sometimes supported by semi-slave work (Gutierrez 2018; Palmer 2014). One example is the extraction of cobalt, necessary for lithium-ion batteries prevalent in portable devices, which puts thousands of children to work in countries like Congo (Amnesty International 2016, 29). The Haiti deployment, for example, relied heavily on mobile phones, which in the chaos created by the earthquake, were the only means of communication (Hesse 2010). Other problematic issues include the power asymmetries embedded in datasets and present in the relationship between the deployers, who are the gatekeeping the map, and reporters enduring the crisis on the ground.

However imperfect, the Haiti map saved lives (Meier 2012), transforming humanitarianism (Bernholz et al. 2010; Meier 2015a, 2015b; Owen 2015; Verity 2011) and illuminating what Harley called “cartographic power” (1989: 12).

Maps are vehicles for power (Harley 2002: 7; Scharl & Tochtermann 2007: vii-viii). They signify and endow it: a map can convey the meaning of power and different forms of control can be exerted by it (Harley 2002: 7). They are “social constructions that work politically” to influence the way we interpret the world, sustain particular discourses about it and impact the lives of the people in the territory they depict (Fotiadis 2008: 1).

As effective political media, the state has traditionally monopolised their circulation. In fact, the map used to be “the perfect symbol of the state” (Monmonier 1991: 88). But a shift in power relations occurs when people, instead of states, exercise their cartographic power and enact their “spatial citizenship,” that is, the ability and entitlement to participate in societal spatial decision-making or geoparticipation (Pánek 2016; Spacit 2017).

People and activists have been exercising their spatial citizenship in defiance of authority for decades (Mesquita 2013). The capabilities of the geospatial web or geoweb –which combines geographic, geospatial and geotag overlay systems (Scharl & Tochtermann 2007)—, the crowdsourcing platforms’ capability of gathering and visualising citizen data, the penetration of mobile technologies and the access to other infrastructures, such as remote sensing systems, have “extended” people’s cartographic power in McLuhanian terms (McLuhan, 1994:103). In Pickles’s words, people have been creating “new

cartographies for new worlds” (2004: 161). But what have the consequences for humanitarianism and activism been?

Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia are typical examples of geoactivism. They exemplify the effects that the geoweb has on humanitarianism and activism, which could be categorised as a paradigm shift, several disruptions and criticism. Based on in-depth interviews with key actors, two case studies and empirical observation, this paper examines how these fields of power and knowledge are being reconfigured by new cartographic practices.

Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia are early approaches to geoactivism and share some similarities, while they differ in objectives and how they gather data. The different applications of these platforms examined here illustrate the foundation of geoactivism, augmenting the understanding of how cartography is being used to reinterpret reality, enhance communication, empower people, facilitate action, and challenge the established narratives and power relationships as well.

The article is organised as follows: First comes a methodological note. The next section proposes a conceptual toolkit for this study, which does not intend to be a wide-ranging review of all cases and theories but a selection of notions that can be useful to explore geoactivism. Next, the two platforms are compared. The central section deals with the outcomes derived from the application of the geoweb to humanitarianism and activism. The conclusions ponder on the analysis and new research questions for further study.

Methodology

Data were collected through empirical observation, case studies and qualitative interviewing.

The analysis draws on Gutiérrez (2018), where attributes spotted in forty data projects, thirty semi-structured interviews with data practitioners, activists and experts, a case study and four in-depth interviews with Ushahidi developers and deployers served as the groundwork for a classification employed in inspecting real-life cases of data infrastructure usage in humanitarianism and activism. The sampling criteria applied to decide on the interviewees comprise the following: interviewees use the data infrastructure in their work, they frequently describe themselves as data journalists or data activists, or are researchers in those fields, and they employ data analysis and visualisations with a humanitarian or social goal (*ibid.*). The range of interviewees was planned to capture the diversity of insights.

For this article, five of these interviewees –chosen for their in-depth knowledge of the Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia platforms— were questioned again about the role of maps in humanitarianism and activism. Consequently, additional questionnaires were sent to these experts and practitioners around the following research questions:

RQ1: How do humanitarianism and activism use maps?

RQ2: What have been the consequences of crisis maps for humanitarianism? Or what have been the consequences of activist maps for activism?

Interviewee 1 is a former manager at Ushahidi; Interviewee 2 is a Ushahidi platform deployer and a UN official specialised in information and coordination systems in emergencies; Interviewee 3 is a former manager at Ushahidi and an authority on crisis and activist mapping; Interviewee 4 is a current manager at Ushahidi; and Interviewee 5 is a current manager at InfoAmazonia.

The rationale behind the interviews is to capture what these activists and practitioners believe they do (Balsiger & Lambelet 2014; Bernard 2006; Cohen & Crabtree 2006). Open-ended questions (i.e. “How do you use maps in your work?”) were used in semi-structured questionnaires –designed to last for 30-45 minutes—, sent by email or formulated in phone conversations.

The case study methodology employed to look at deployments of the Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia platforms intends to show what maps in geoactivism look like based not on what actors say, but on maps, evaluations, scientific literature, commentary and website content (Woodside 2010: 322). This is a single-focused, descriptive study that utilises two instances to provide a common framework for future studies (*ibid.*: 322). Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia provide cases for a class of phenomena: geoactivism, or activism that utilises interactive maps for knowledge, coordination and action. The case study methodology is helpful when the boundaries between a phenomenon and its context are not evident (Yin 2002, 13). These organisations have been chosen because contextual conditions are pertinent to the exploration of geoactivism and both sit at the intersection of several trends, namely the social uses of the data and communication infrastructures, data journalism, critical cartography, digital humanitarianism and collective action. Only the aspects relevant to the employment of maps in humanitarianism and activism are included here.

Finally, using empirical observation, other pertinent cases are also integrated into the analysis to clarify particular aspects of geoactivism.

Towards a conceptual toolkit for geoactivism

Under names such as “critical cartography,” “crisis mapping,” “grassroots mapping,” “community mapping,” “volunteered geographic information,” “counter-mapping” and “radical cartography,” among others, new cartographic practices and applications of geospatial technologies are increasingly popular in humanitarianism and activism. These labels denote different things; this section deals with how these concepts relate to the case studies.

A map is a map

According to Denil, maps should comply with the criteria of “mapicity” –that is, they must be recognised by communities of users as useful, usable and believable as maps (2011). Maps in geoactivism display additional characteristics: they are extremely time-sensitive, and they foster participation and action.

Firstly, cartographic interpretations have always been time-sensitive. They need to be interpreted in their context (Harley 2009: 130) since they are “like milk: their information is perishable, and it is wise to check the date” (Monmonier 1991: 54). In the era of the geoweb, acquiring the dimension of sequential time, sometimes even real-time, the map becomes dynamic. Interviewee 2 describes it like this:

An interactive map in digital humanitarianism has long ceased to be a two-dimensional representation. It is a dynamic system that allows you to upload and manage localised reports in a timeline, and modify their statuses in near-real-time (...). Dynamic maps are more comparable to a movie that allows you to understand what is going on and respond accordingly in real-time.

Crisis maps are living creatures: they are implanted when an emergency strikes; if they are nurtured, they flourish, and they die when the crisis ceases to be critical, or the mapmakers quit. Timely action in humanitarianism is fundamental, which explains why the Ushahidi platform –the first in incorporating time-bounded crowdsourced data into evolving humanitarian operations– has been so impactful. Interviewee 3 puts it like this:

It meant a shift in the nature of data, which could be organised in a spatial and sequential context at a tremendous velocity and in a multimedia format that could associate text, audio, video and pictures. It was a change in the information ecosystem that enabled the maps to represent quasi-real-time, which radically opened up all kind of political and humanitarian opportunities for more targeted, informed decision-making.

In short, in the geoweb, space and time are entwined. This quality allows activists and humanitarians to overcome the three significant challenges of mapping narratives too: maps enable the pinpointing of places associated with stories; the representation of connections between places and stories; and the integration of a temporal dimension to the overall narrative (Caquard & Fiset 2014: 24). This association with finite processes makes geoactivist maps ephemeral.

Secondly, maps in geoactivism are more than geography, geometry and time; they can promote participation. What follows is an effort to untangle a jumble of notions related to bottom-up mapping practices in light of geoactivism.

Grassroots mapping or community mapping uses “participatory geographic information systems” or PGIS (Abbot et al. 2001). These practices produce an “alternative, community-owned definition of a territory” by collecting data via civic science, or science that questions the state of things (Dosemagen et al. 2011). I call these data “citizen data” for short. Grassroots and community cartography can tell a story about what is happening in communities (National Community Mapping Institute 2018).

Volunteered geographic information (known as VGI or “volunteered geography” (Bishr and Mantelas 2008: 211-229) could also be considered as part of grassroots mapping, as it is the art of creating and disseminating spatial data provided by citizens, who become then sensors (Goodchild 2007). While the accent in PGIS is on the participatory process and outcomes, VGI stresses the application and data (Verplanke et al. 2016).

This second property of geoactivism is part of a broader phenomenon called user-generated content. Resembling citizens’ media (Rodríguez 2001), this idea emphasises the leading role that ordinary citizens take in collectively engaging in data-gathering exercises and generating maps.

Many Ushahidi's and InfoAmazonia's applications could be considered grassroots, participatory, community and volunteered, as they place mapping, in Turner's words, "within reach of users and developers" (2006: 1).

At Ushahidi, witnesses of a crisis typically submit reports by text messaging, email or web postings, and the software aggregates and organises the data into a map and a timeline (Sheller 2015). The deployers categorise the information, so it is helpful to other users. For "Ayuda Ecuador," the platform was set up by a community of digital humanitarians working remotely, among them Interviewee 2. The idea was "to collectively generate data relevant to the emergency, threats, logistic needs and response that the affected population was experiencing" (Ayuda Ecuador 2016). "Ayuda Ecuador" showed hundreds of reports from April 16 to May 5, categorised as "emergencies," "threats" and "logistics," among others, which then branched out in subcategories indicating action and places.

Another example can be found in participative water management. Local authorities often lack the resources to integrate local knowledge into their plans (Dungumaro & Madulu 2003; Hohenthal et al. 2017: 383). Instead of waiting for top-down solutions to their water problems, the communities in the West of Pará, Brazil, linked by "Rede InfoAmazonia," share measurements of the quality and quantity of water to be able to make decisions in their daily lives. The initiative connects a network of sensors managed by the communities via mobile phones "capable of monitoring physical and chemical parameters that help indicate whether the water is contaminated" (Rede InfoAmazonia 2016). The idea is to produce warnings about the quality of the water, as well as to gather historical data, visualise them on a map and identify trends.

Accordingly, Salovaara uses the term "participatory maps" to allude to InfoAmazonia's maps and other digital cartographies (2016). Participatory mapping is an accepted term linked with grassroots and counter-mapping practices, as IFAD notes in a review. Some participatory mapping initiatives have empowered grassroots efforts to hold governments responsible for bad judgement related to land and resource use and distribution (IFAD 2009).

However, other mapping activities promoted by InfoAmazonia, which crowdsources and visualises stories by journalists and activists from the nine Amazonian countries as well, cannot be considered grassroots, as they are produced by experts and not by ordinary people. That is, not all geoactivism is grassroots or citizens' mapping, as geoactivist actors can include experts based in hierarchical structures.

Besides, not all grassroots mapping is geoactivism for two reasons. First, "not all participatory mapping is digital" (Social Life 2015) or supported by the geoweb; second, participatory mapping does not necessarily is direct to supporting humanitarian or advocacy efforts.

Equally, not all the geoactivist cases can be considered VGI. Ushahidi maps typically depend on three communities: the digital humanitarians launching and managing the deployment from remote locations (deployers); the humanitarian agencies, using the information on the ground; and the people affected by the emergency, reporting data and using the information (reporters). Some of the maps are totally volunteered, and others are the product of collaboration between volunteers and salaried experts. Interviewee 2 explains:

Let's be clear about this. When we are paid to do this job, we can be digital humanitarians, but we are certainly not volunteers (...). Digital humanitarians can be salaried "respondents" (that is, I, for example) and expert volunteers working *pro bono*. They all contribute their knowledge and support.

Thus, these terms exhibit ample areas of intersection but are not to be used as synonyms in observing geoactivism.

The third property of maps in geoactivism is their ability to foster action. The spaces created by geoactivism are not pure communication or representation; they embed a teleological expectation of action, either in humanitarianism or advocacy.

Reports of "threats" on the "Ayuda Ecuador" map were not published simply to denounce a menace; reporting witnesses deliver data on threats and deployers work so opportune action is delivered. In humanitarianism, a verified report must result in urgent action because lives are at stake; and obtaining data depends on the contribution of motivated crowds and digital humanitarians based on the prospect of future engagement. Likewise, "Rede InfoAmazonia's" warnings are produced with a prospect of action as well. In activism, maps serve to support demands, only with longer timeframes.

Talking about the 15M movement in Spain, de Soto's description of this movement's cartography serves to illustrate how interactive maps entice action. The 15M maps (Figure 5) were vehicles of "processes of self-organisation, distributed and decentralised action, inclusiveness of diverse actors and processes of social imagination" (de Soto 2014: 1). During the protests that marched against

massive evictions and austerity programmes across Spain in 2012, people appropriated maps as both analysis and action tools (ibid.: 2). As action tools, they facilitated “the transformation of people’s anger and discomfort into power and fearlessness,” and they advanced the organisation of a collective response (ibid.).

Similarly, maps at Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia serve to transform the feeling of penury and sadness into proactiveness, and to organise and mobilise solutions and help collectively. This third characteristic depends on the two features described before: timeliness and participation.

Activism and humanitarianism

Hereafter “activism” is understood as actions aimed at fostering, obstructing or guiding socioeconomic, political or environmental change. Activism involves developing a theory of change and is directed at medium- and long-term causes. Meanwhile, “humanitarianism” comprises the short-term efforts involved in offering material and logistic help, and responding to disasters and emergencies, mediating in conflicts and carrying out peacekeeping operations (Chandler 2012; Chopard & Lusser 1997; Dijkzeul & Moke 2005).

Although many organisations are hybrid, humanitarian agencies get in and out the crisis at hand rapidly with the objective of saving lives (Gutierrez 2018). Humanitarianism’s transient character goes hand in hand with the fleeting nature of crisis maps, which last only as long as the crisis and the enthusiasm of the maps’ supporters persist (ibid.).

Digital humanitarianism is humanitarianism that employs data crowdsourcing platforms and interactive maps for action in emergencies. Digital humanitarians are experts trained in spatial and communication techniques that assist in emergencies from different locations (Meier 2015a). As seen earlier, they can be expert volunteers or salaried specialists.

Meanwhile, activist organisations can go from being proactive (i.e. negotiating) to being reactive (i.e. protesting), depending on how open the door for collaboration with authorities is in each situation (ibid.).

Both humanitarianism and activism enabled by spatial information can be considered geoactivism, or practices that enable people’s engagement with spatial technologies to communicate, empower and act. Geoactivism includes both “crisis mapping” and “activist mapping.” Crisis mapping has the potential to immediately improve the situation on the ground and aid humanitarian assistance, as Interviewee 1 explains:

It is quite a specific set of abilities that are needed in crises. When a crisis occurs, the first 24-48 hours are very important (...). So, (crisis mapping) is the act of managing crisis reports and mapping them, and channelling the information to responders on the ground, and being able to do that very quickly.

While most Ushahidi maps are deployed to tackle emergencies and are short-lived (i.e. flooding), InfoAmazonia’s cartography usually lasts longer and deals with underlying causes (i.e. climate change). Accordingly, Interviewee 1 distinguishes between crisis mapping and activist mapping:

(Crisis mapping) is the act of receiving reports during a crisis or an emergency about a request or location of services, and plotting them on a map (...). (But for activist mapping) many times (the issue at hand) is not that urgent, although it can be if victims need help. But it is usually a longer-term activity, more focused on gathering bodies of evidence that can be used for lobbying and advocacy.

This differentiation is useful when examining specific initiatives.

Critical, counter-mapping and radical cartography

“Critical cartography” is a theoretical critique of conventional cartography (Perkins 2008: 150). It can refer also to a set of mapping practices, including “mapping the unmapped” (MIT SLAB 2017) – “unmasking of the silences in traditional maps” (Pickles 2004: 183)–, “counter-mapping” and “radical cartography.” The differences between these labels can serve to look at the case studies.

Linking geographic knowledge to political power, theoretical critical cartography offers “new ways of understanding” the changes that happen when people create and use maps (Perkins 2008: 150). The central idea in critical cartography is that maps, as data (Gitelman 2013), are never neutral, and therefore, in the hands of people, as opposed to the state, maps correct power imbalances and acquire

different qualities. No map is flawless, as the cartographers in Borges's tale yearned for (2007). In "On Exactitude in Science," Borges tells about an empire where seeking faithfulness, cartographers try to produce maps as big as the territory they represent. Eventually, these maps were abandoned and forgotten. Being unmanageable, one can say these maps lose their mapicity. The tale supports the idea that "the map is not the territory" (Korzybski 1994: 58). Besides, as any dataset, the data maps are based on are not free of ideology, as data do not emerge independently of the opinions, methods, values and technologies of the people that conceive, produce, process, manage, analyse and store them (Lauriault 2012).

According to theoretical critical cartography, then, the same way that conventional maps can reflect relations of power in the interest of dominant elites (Crampton 2003; Harley 2002, 2009), new maps can chart new desires and hopes onto the landscape (Firth 2015). That is, maps can project utopias – a term invented by Thomas More, which means "nowhere" (1684) because they represent better worlds yet to be discovered or created. In geoactivism, this is precisely the ultimate role of maps because, paraphrasing Firth, geoactivist maps can be used to make "practical plans for social change or to imagine utopian worlds" (2015). Interviewee 2 puts it like this:

(Maps) cannot predict the future, but they can provide useful information and show clear patterns that allow you to think about, imagine and plan the future. The vision of a better world can be represented on a map showing 'we need to get there.' If you want to think of a better world, you should not just dream it, but instead, establish where and when this better world is going to happen. That is how maps are useful. A good map helps you understand how to get there.

Critical cartography, as said, can be a set of practices. For example, critical mapping can fill cartographic silences. The Haiti Ushahidi deployment, again, is an example. Although it was not its primary objective, the map ended up showing parts of Haiti previously uncharted (Meier 2012). Another example is Map Kibera, a community-based project that filled the blank spot on the map that the neighbourhood of Kibera, Nairobi, was until November 2009, when a group of locals created the first digital map of their community (Map Kibera 2017).

The practice of critical cartography can be considered counter-mapping too – understood as a mapping practice exercised against dominant power structures (Peluso 1995). This term stresses the disruptive character of bottom-up mapping practices. Counter-mapping emerged in resistance to governmental initiatives that rechart land to hand over pieces of the commons to businesses for commercial operation, for example, in Indonesia (ibid.). It started as a tool to claim back traditional territories for indigenous and local communities. "Challenging state power over maps and its categorisation of land uses," counter-mapping has become "an important movement" (Radjawali & Pye 2015: 4).

The first deployment of the Ushahidi platform demonstrates the defiant nature of counter-maps. More than 850 people died in attacks against different ethnic communities loyal to either President Mwai Kibaki or opposition leader Raila Odinga in 2008 (Smith 2008). The number of deaths was "grossly underreported" by the government, police and media, while the truth emerged only in disjointed accounts from family and friends (Okolloh 2008). Ory Okolloh, a blogger in Nairobi, together with three fellow activists, created a mapping tool that would assign numbers, stories and names to the dead (ibid.), mapping the unmapped and gainsaying the official version. It was the start of Ushahidi, "testimony" in Swahili.

Finally, critical mapping can be radical as well. True "cartographic radicality" requires the map to replace accepted schema of mapicity (Denil 2011). That is, cartographic radicality can be located in the possibility of map schemas to change. Radical maps "introduce into the schema elements or approaches that open avenues of usability previously held inaccessible, invisible or perhaps even undesirable" (ibid.). An illustration is InfoAmazonia's "Floods Alerts," which enhances the map's usability by linking it to alert systems, a feature is not present in conventional maps. The map warns vulnerable populations through mobile technologies and automated monitoring of river levels about floods (InfoAmazonia 2017b).

Another way in which the canons of conventional map schemas are ruptured in geoactivism is by incorporating new actors into the mapping process. Echoing Chambers when he talks in his participatory rural appraisal research about how local people make maps, diagram, present information and plan (1994), Interviewee 4 puts it like this:

What we have done, and this is quite radical, is broadening the definition of who is an *expert*. Local knowledge is extremely important, and people without formal education can be experts on

how things are to be done. The question is how you tap into that expertise (...). There is a lot of local expertise, and things that seem very simple are not that simple at all.

To examine the radicality of maps in geoactivism, it is interesting to observe them from the perspective of radical media and citizens' media, which are distinct but overlapping concepts. The mediating role of a map manifests as it becomes "a signifying system through which a social order *is* communicated, reproduced, experienced and explored" (Harley 2002: 45). Once established as media, maps' alternativeness could be considered a way to "express an alternative vision of hegemonic policies, priorities and perspectives," paraphrasing Downing (2004: v). For Downing, alternative media are diverse, provocative and marginal, and produced outside mainstream institutions (2011: 15). In contrast, Rodríguez proposes to abandon "alternative media" for "citizens' media," because the first notion "rests on the assumption that these media are alternative to something" and highlights an "oppositional thinking" that disregards other forms of bottom-up media practices (2001: 20). However, the same way that "radical media" as a concept sets some types of citizens' media aside because they lack a confrontational nature, "citizens' media" sets some types of alternative media aside as well because, however diverse, provocative and marginal, they are not bottom-up projects.

The first Ushahidi map was radical and alternative in that it was published in defiance of the government's and mainstream media's version of events, and in that it enhanced the usability of maps in unconventional ways and introduced new actors in mapmaking. It was also grassroots in that it was produced based on citizen data, although the process was mediated by the platform and the rules of verification and categorisation established by the deployers. But most Ushahidi's maps are not confrontational. To be able to intervene in situations of crisis, humanitarians have to work with the authorities. Consequently, as Ushahidi's Director of Community Engagement Oduor says, her organisation "encourages collaboration (with authorities)" (Gutierrez 2018).

Meanwhile, Forensic Architecture's chart of the Saynaya prison, in Syria, is radical, without being grassroots. This geoactivist organisation employed architectural and acoustic modelling, based on former prisoners' experiences of detention, to plot the Saynaya prison, near Damascus. Saynaya is a place where torture and executions are practised on political prisoners (Amnesty International 2017). In 2016, Forensic Architecture met Saynaya survivors to visualise the sounds from their memories on a map, which is not flat, but spherical in a McLuhanian sense, as it is a "multisensory and multidimensional space" (McLuhan & McLuhan 1992: 18). This makes the Saynaya prison chart radical, but not grassroots.

Table 1: How alternative these maps are

	Mapping the unmapped	Counter-maps	Radical cartography	Volunteered geography	Grassroots/citizens' mapping
Ushahidi	Occasionally	√	√	Not always	√
InfoAmazonia	√	√	√	Not always	Not always

Source: Elaboration by the author.

Geoactivism can fill gaps and can be considered counter-mapping, radical, volunteered, grassroots and citizens' cartography, but these terms are not interchangeable as they cannot be applied to all geoactivist cases (see Table 1). Real cases show variations. Using Rodríguez's concept of the *mediascape* (2001), the reality is more complicated than the traditional views on media reveal.

Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia: Description and contrast

Ushahidi

Ushahidi today is a non-profit company that develops software able to collect and visualise citizen data, information and action through interactive mapping. Anybody willing to launch a map can have free access to essential features, including unlimited posts, one survey, one user, web and email data collection and a map (Ushahidi 2017). Monthly fees give deployers more usability and customisation (ibid.). Ushahidi also trains people to use its platform, creates communities and occasionally launches its own deployments (Georgiadou et al. 2011: 296).

Since its creation, the platform has been used in every significant catastrophe around the world, expanding to non-violent issues and activist mapping, for example, the anti-corruption movements in Brazil, Morocco, and Indonesia (Were 2015). By 2017, it had achieved 120,000 deployments and 10 million testimonies (Ushahidi 2017).

Maps at Ushahidi depend on crowds volunteering reports. Doing so, Ushahidi deployments get advantage of the three benefits of leveraging crowdsourced data for disaster assistance identified by Gao

et al. (2011: 11). The first one is the immediacy of data collection. An example, again, is the Haiti deployment, which was set up in two hours (ibid.). A second advantage comes from a macro perspective. Any Ushahidi map with sufficient reports provides a high-resolution landscape of a crisis. The third benefit comes from a micro perspective. Since the map can include information sent from any device, relief organisations can accurately locate individual requests for help (ibid.).

Crowds can be leveraged as knowledge producers, as sources, as analysts and as communities (Pawlak & Ricci 2014), presenting elements that open uncharted avenues and radicalising the map in Denil's terms (2011). Ushahidi has mastered the use of crowds as knowledge generators, (i.e. enabling communities to geotag reports), sources (i.e. crowdsourcing services), and communities (i.e. rallying digital humanitarians) (Gutiérrez 2018). Crowds as analysts can be leveraged to inspect drone-based aerial images, for instance (Meier 2015b). Before drones, balloons and kites were employed to take over 100,000 pictures from regions impacted by the Deepwater Horizon oil spill in the Gulf of Mexico (Dosemagen et al. 2011). Crowds were used too to analyse the resulting pictures and plot over eighty maps of the coastline (ibid.). That is, crisis mapping is often enabled and constrained by a new actor in mapmaking: crowds.

Lacking credibility in target communities, many Ushahidi deployments have been abandoned right after having been launched (Slater 2016). Creating maps by default has become so customary that Leson recommends that social groups setting up deployments should start by asking themselves: "why a map?" (2016). An analysis based on almost 13,000 deployments indicates, for example, that 93% had fewer than ten reports while 61% had not been customised or used (Bailard et al. 2012; Vota 2012). Digital humanitarianism combines information and emotion, which need each other to mobilise people effectively; failure to generate trustworthiness and motivate relevant communities prompts a "dead Ushahidi" map with no crowd behind (Vota 2016).

Having access to correct information in a crisis leads to targeted actions. If crisis maps are based on a collection of reports from different sources, there has to be a system for verification. Ushahidi founders realised this was the case early on, and a system to authenticate testimonies was established (Smith 2008). Although anyone can start an Ushahidi map and send a report, only its administrators can publish them. Nevertheless, this system has not forestalled some glitches (Ford 2012).

InfoAmazonia

The environmental loss is one of the best examples of how global phenomena impact local communities. The Amazon is the backdrop of a human security crisis exacerbated by the promotion of conflicting activities (Simmons 2002: 255). Despite this rainforest's role in the global climate systems, only fragmented information is available about the risks that loom over it. Meanwhile, new infrastructure and agricultural projects causing deforestation proceed. InfoAmazonia is attempting to fill this information gap utilising the accessible data from satellites, which are transforming environmental reporting by "mapping environmental damage, endangered species and human-made disasters" (Salovaara 2016: 827). Figure 2 shows the InfoAmazonia deforestation map, including layers of data from different periods, ready to be downloaded and used.

Figure 2: InfoAmazonia's deforestation map

Source: (InfoAmazonia 2017c)

Launched during the UN Conference on Sustainable Development in Rio de Janeiro in 2012, InfoAmazonia is an online facility that generates and gathers investigative stories, maps and advocacy from organisations, citizens, and journalists about the Amazon region (InfoAmazonia 2017a). It also provides training for journalists, campaigners and communities about how to use satellite imagery, create maps and collect data; advocates for open data; deploys sensors, and builds mobile applications (ibid.).

Bypassing mainstream media gatekeepers to communicate directly with broader audiences (Hackett & Carroll 2006: 47), InfoAmazonia shows a degree of hybridisation, crossing lines between journalism and activism.

Contrast

Triggered by crises and issues, Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia share the fact that they place the mapping process and its actors at the centre, and that they work in the intersection of the local and global. They differ in objectives and how they gather data.

Caquard and Cartwright note the importance of looking behind the scenes at the mapping process to explore “the potential of maps as narratives” (2014: 101). Ushahidi’s open mapping process offers a glimpse of the relationship between the map and its makers. The open interface of the project management application Trello in Figure 3 presents how the Ushahidi deployment “Ayuda Ecuador,” launched after the first tremors of the earthquake on April 16, 2016, was still developing a month later and who was doing what. The transparency and horizontality of the network reinforce the credibility of the deployment, which is fundamental to activate the crowd’s participation.

Figure 3: Coordination behind the “Ayuda Ecuador” map

Source: (Ushahidi Ecuador 2016)

Crisis maps are animated stories where the cartographers are also protagonists, together with the humanitarian workers and the people affected by an emergency. In the case of the activist mapping of InfoAmazonia, the central characters include the managers and providers of the data (i.e. local communities in “Rede InfoAmazonia”) and the journalists and activists delivering the geolocalised stories, as Figure 4 shows.

Figure 4: Elena Calle’s story on the InfoAmazonia deforestation map

Source: (Calle 2017)

These maps highlight the sense of place –the map’s local dimension— as well. Places shape stories, just as stories produce “spatial identities” (Caquard & Fiset 2014: 18). In InfoAmazonia, the environmental and humanitarian realities of the region determine the reports that emerge from it, while these stories weave a tapestry of spatial identity for the region, a part of which can be observed in Figure 4.

The local and the global are also patent in how these platforms operate, taking advantage of the “space of flows,” which allows real-time social practices to happen simultaneously (Castells 1992, 2010). In Ushahidi, for example, digital humanitarians work globally to gather data from the ground, which comes back to the local via the map, showing verified information, coordination and action which is usable on the ground.

Table 2: Comparison of approaches (Ushahidi vs InfoAmazonia).

	Ushahidi	InfoAmazonia
Deployers/reporters	Anybody without central control; sometimes Ushahidi	Journalists and activists with some centralised editorial control
Data origin	Crowdsourced citizen data (scraped data to verify data)	Crowdsourced, generated by communities (i.e. sensors), public data (i.e. satellite imagery), and new stories, analysis and campaign content
Objectives	Immediate action (“crisis mapping”)	Medium-, long-term causes (“activist mapping”)
Beginnings	Citizen’s journalism and activism	Journalism

Source: Elaboration by the author.

Table 2 shows a comparison between Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia based on their actors, data, objectives and roots. Scholars have struggled to find labels for what people do in the geoweb (Elwood 2010: 350); and looking at the source of the data and the objectives of the specific cases can help with the labelling. For example, using Gutiérrez (2018), Ushahidi is a geoactivist initiative based on crowdsourced data, while InfoAmazonia is mainly a producer of map-based journalism and activism, which also transfers skills and generates advocacy outputs, and gets data from a variety of sources.

Three outcomes

Humanity has continually been looking for mapping systems that explain the world. But as this society is “unmanageably large and changing,” it only allows imperfect mapping, which means that we are in a “constant process of self-discovery and self-making” (Jarvie, 1972: 165). Part of this self-discovery process, today’s enhanced maps constitute a visual lingo that needs no translation. They are ubiquitous: they can be found on screens in cars, laptops, wearables and phones. Cartography is popular (Perkins 2008: 150). Although not perfect mapping systems, Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia, among other initiatives of the civil society, are examples of how social organisations are decoding and recoding spatial data,

generating different outcomes in the shape of a paradigm shift, which has spawned disruptions and criticism. This section examines them.

New standards

The paradigm change that geoactivism has bred exhibits two forms: digital maps become a standard in humanitarianism and activism, and their actors change.

The Ushahidi platform has contributed to making cartography easier than ever to the point that thousands of maps are launched every day by default, as seen earlier (Leson 2016). That is, cartography has turned into a routine, and the use of interactive maps in humanitarianism has become what Kuhn would describe as a “commonly accepted standard” (1970). Interviewee 2 explains:

(Today) it is impossible to respond to an emergency without a (crisis) map, (which has turned out to be) one the rare commonalities among all agencies attending any emergency, including health, nutrition, water and sanitation, safety crises... all crises.

The interviewees highlight their dependence on well-informed maps. Even the failure of hundreds of Ushahidi maps reinforces the idea that maps are already taken for granted in geoactivism. Thus, the first outcome that geoactivism poses is the standardisation of digital maps, which in many cases can be deemed as grassroots and radical, as they levy different approaches to make previously unseen objects, people and processes perceptible, and enhance the usability of conventional maps (Denil 2011). Interestingly, as these radical maps become more customary, it is to be assumed that they will start losing their radicality.

As noted earlier, the other consequence of geoactivism is the introduction of new actors in mapmaking. By generating spatial data on their own terms, InfoAmazonia’s and Ushahidi’s users (former data petitioners) are transformed into what Elwood would call data providers (2007: 16). The geoweb represents a change from a model in which “traditional mapping agencies” elaborate “standards and specifications to govern the production of geographic information” (Goodchild 2007: 219), to a new model in which communities are involved in producing datasets that integrate volunteered information (Grossner et al. 2008: 159; Pickles 2004). Consequently, community processes are enhanced by this form spatial citizenship, challenging “the official maps and other spatial representations produced by state authorities and scientists” (Hohenthal et al. 2017: 383).

This change is evident in digital humanitarianism. Not only are non-experts called to participate in humanitarian emergencies alongside with experts; other new actors have emerged. The Haiti deployment was the starting point for a new figure in emergencies: the “digital humanitarian” (Meier 2015a), “techno-humanitarian” (Keim 2012) or “humanitarian technologist” (Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery Labs 2010). From 2010 onwards, digital humanitarians —often professionals with expertise in GIS, database management, social media and online campaigns— started to apply their skills to deal with disasters, inaugurating a new trend of “disruptive philanthropy” (Bernholz et al. 2010).

These two changes are linked with other consequences of geoactivism.

Geoactivism means disruption

Disruption in geoactivism comes first as a way of power redistribution. Since mapping is to be understood as a political process, asking who produces the map and how people can access it is paramount (Radjawali & Pye 2015: 4). Because when geoactivism places muscle in the hands of people, a disturbance of the traditional power relations around maps happens.

The inclusion of different actors in crisis management triggers another irritation in the shape of a change in methodologies. Once the crisis mapping model was tested in 2008, it expanded, challenging hierarchical institutions with entrenched practices, interests and stakeholders (Owen 2015: 7), and defying “the old analogue models of control and command” in humanitarianism (Conneally 2012). Paraphrasing della Porta and Diani, geoactivism is disruptive in that it obstructs the normal course of events (2006: 174). Interviewee 2 elaborates:

Citizen data-based maps in emergencies were, and continue to be, highly disruptive. One of the challenges was to feed information into traditional rescue operations, happening fixedly. An example is “Ayuda Ecuador” last year. Civil servants are used to doing things in specific and predetermined ways. They could not absorb 400 reports in two hours and incorporate them in their dynamics (...). Meanwhile, in traditional humanitarian operations, a situation map can take

a whole day or more to be put together. Trying to combine a citizens' initiative relying on crowdsourced data and a tiered organisation is a big challenge.

Although digital humanitarianism has not been embraced universally by traditional aid organisations (Standby Task Force 2011), its influence has been so strong that it has shaped the way some of them work. The Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) was the first UN agency in integrating crowdsourced data and digital humanitarians in the crisis mapping of Libya (Verity 2011). This collaboration has influenced OCHA's work regarding the speed of producing relevant data in the early phases of an emergency and the coordination between the information management teams with the self-organised volunteers, which was a significant culture change (ibid.).

Another disruption is the strengthening of the evidence in activism and humanitarianism. Radical mapping is not a new phenomenon, but in the past it was easier to be dismissed by people in power. In contrast with aerial photography, high-resolution images supplied by drones and satellites cannot be set aside so lightly (Radjawali & Pye 2015: 12). In the imagery displayed by Google Earth, for example, each pixel on a computer screen represents 60cm on the ground, which allows glimpsing "even individual trees and logs" (Timber Investigation Centre 2017). The ability to zoom in on a single tree expands the story-telling capacities of journalists and activists, according to Interviewee 5:

It has brought the principles of scale and resolution to the journalistic story-telling. You can look at events at the smallest scale, attaching a story to each pixel. It is about treating maps as a bare canvas and using it to tell stories; making geolocalised data confer context to stories and the other way around. That is, generating a dialogue between the data and the stories. It treats individual people as protagonists in a landscape.

Lastly, disruption in geoactivism comes as a change in the maps' usability (Denil 2011). Apart from other alterations in their usability explored earlier, elasticity is another property of grassroots cartography, which makes them suitable for action. To explain maps in activism, de Soto refers to the notion of *rhizome*, coined by Deleuze and Guattari (an idea taken from botany). Rhizomes conform to several principles: among others, the principle of connection and heterogeneity since "any point of a rhizome can be connected to any other" (Deleuze et al., 1987: 7), and the principle of "a signifying rupture," since "a rhizome may be broken, but it will start up again on one of its old lines" (ibid.: 7-9). Based on these concepts, de Soto understands the 15M maps as "action," as flexible networks and supported not by irreplaceable leaders, but by a "connected multitude" whose nodes are expendable (de Soto 2014: 361-368). These qualities make grassroots mapping especially appropriate to represent flexible networks, the structure of many geoactivist organisations (Gutiérrez 2018). Figure 5 shows an instant of the animated map displaying the propagation of 15M protest messages across Spain.

Figure 5: Propagation of 15M messages from April 25 until 26 May 2011

Source: (de Soto 2014: 361).

Thus, disruptions in geoactivism are created by the emergence of new actors and protocols in humanitarianism; the augmentation of counter-mapping power, and the elasticity of maps for action. These disruptions embed several forms of criticism as well, as seen next.

The critical in geoactivism

Geoactivism begets criticism, which can be described as a challenge to conventional, top-down perspectives and massive surveillance. Since its cartography “notices people and things that are overlooked or denied” (MIT SLAB 2017), geoactivism embodies a critique of the *status quo*. It questions the authority of state agencies and experts who regard maps as “static representations of the constellations of physical elements in space” (Hohenthal et al. 2017: 384).

In 2011, after the Fukushima Daiichi accident, for example, Safecast was set up by a team of hackers to generate radiation maps measuring radionuclide contamination across Japan, based on a network of sensors (Hemmi & Graham 2013: 830). Hemmi and Graham compare the successful Safecast with the official initiative KURAMA, established by the University of Tokyo, to conclude that “the open Safecast community was able to build their system at lower cost by enrolling volunteers, gaining crowdsourced donations, creating a global forum to discuss methods, and using open-source components” (ibid.). Likewise, criticism emerges when geoactivists supply needed information in the absence of institutional support. Instead of waiting for top-down solutions, “Rede InfoAmazonia” produces its own maps, water measurements and alert systems. That is, bottom-up initiatives such as Safecast and “Rede InfoAmazonia” comprise an implicit criticism of officialdom.

The emergence of GIS, which allows the mining, storage, analysis and visualisation of spatial data, make *geosurveillance* possible. Geosurveillance –or the monitoring of geolocalised activities (Crampton 2003: 146)— is one of the tools of “computational politics” (Tufekci 2014), or what Braman calls the “informational state” (2009: 314), which enables massive collection and exploitation of private data by governments and corporations, threatening civil rights (Gangadharan 2012; O’Neil 2016).

But the power relationship between the surveilled and the surveillants can be altered. The rise of the geoweb has been linked to shifts in the processes and power relations of spatial data creation and use (Elwood 2010: 349). Geoactivism can transform surveilled people into surveillants, enabling a form of bottom-up *sousveillance* –namely, an “inverse (geo)surveillance” (Mann et al. 2003: 338–348).

An example is Bellingcat, a website that generates maps through the analysis of satellite imagery and crowdsourced images posted in social networks. Since 2012, it uses open source intelligence by analysing and tracking military equipment appearing in pictures and videos shared via social media networks. In 2014, this organisation became famous by implying that it was the Russian army who stroke the Malaysia Airlines Flight 17 down in Ukraine, based on images published in social media of a Russian

convoy carrying anti-aircraft artillery across Ukraine (Bellingcat 2014). Bellingcat has provided evidence of the Syrian war and the 2014-2015 Russian military intervention in Ukraine, among other events (ibid.), challenging state geosurveillance.

Many organisations and communities are stressing the absence of technology and information around vital issues, addressing the politics of data, questioning data and agency, inviting people to shape issues, and generating alternative epistemologies in a datafied environment (Milan & van der Velden 2016: 1; Zanello & Maassen 2011). Paraphrasing Wood, geoactivism comprises a sharp criticism of conventional cartography, signifying a departure from previous approaches to mapmaking and showing “where mapping is headed” (2010: 111).

Discussion and conclusions

Geoactivism refers to the employment of digital maps, data crowdsourcing platforms and other infrastructures to provide alternative narratives, and spaces for communication, coordination and action in humanitarianism and activism. The geoweb affords maps enhanced properties: they cease to be simple geographic representations of terrain and acquire sequential dynamism. In geoactivism, digital maps gain new properties: near-real-time data makes them ephemeral, and they become action-oriented, participatory and production tools signifying complex social, political or technological processes, and mutable interactions and networks for participation and action.

The Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia, among other geoactivist platforms, are examples of how activism is incorporating mapping practices. Although not all concepts associated with critical cartography –which sees the political in maps— apply consistently to all cases of geoactivism, geoactivist cartography can fill gaps, mapping the unmapped (i.e. Map Kibera), and be counter-mapping (i.e. the first deployment of the Ushahidi in Kenya), radical (i.e. the warning systems included in some InfoAmazonia’s maps), volunteered (i.e. most deployments of the Ushahidi platform), and grassroots (i.e. the remapping of land in Indonesia).

Both Ushahidi and InfoAmazonia place the mapping process and its actors at the centre and work at the intersection of the local and global. They differ mainly in objectives and how they gather data, as Ushahidi crowdsources citizen data for quasi-real-time emergency assistance, producing crisis maps, while InfoAmazonia resorts to more varied sources of data to deal with longer-term issues, producing activist maps and empowering people.

By engaging in critical cartography, geoactivism has produced paradigmatic, disruptive and critical outcomes. The first include the standardisation of digital maps and the inclusion of new actors in the cartographic processes of humanitarianism and activism. The disruptions generated by geoactivism comprise changes in the usability of maps, in mapping power relations and methodologies, as well as in the strengthening of humanitarianism and activism by making data-based evidence more robust. Finally, geoactivism embeds a strong criticism of top-down cartographic approaches and massive governmental and corporate surveillance as well.

Figure 7 shows how these outcomes are connected: the emergence of digital maps as a standard in humanitarianism and activism is linked with the acquisition of new usabilities (redicalisation) and the criticism towards conventional cartography. The integration of new actors in mapping processes is associated with changes in methodologies and power relations around maps within humanitarianism and activism.

Figure 7: Outcomes of geoactivism and their associations

Source: Elaboration by the author.

Because of what they do, these maps are action. They express a form of technopolitics, whose emergence is prompted by the unparalleled access to technology, but whose evolution and strategies are grounded on previous trends, including, but not limited to journalism, alternative and citizens' media (Milan & Gutierrez 2017) and critical cartography. They represent a form of technopolitics from the bottom-up, which has been able to challenge the traditional way of understanding humanitarianism and activism.

The classifications offered in this article are not normative or comprehensive, as they raise more questions than answers. How do radical maps lose their radicality in humanitarianism and activism? What other forms of usability will they develop? How effective are geoactivist maps? Although geoactivism is no panacea, as the cybergraveyards of Ushahidi "dead maps" show, it represents a turning point in humanitarianism and activism. Wilde said that a map of the world that "does not include Utopia is not worth even glancing at" (Wilde 1891: 13). In the hands of geoactivists, utopias ("nowheres") are becoming maputopias ("somewheres"). By ascribing longitude, latitude and time to dreams, geoactivists are making their maps worth glancing at.

Compliance with Ethics Requirements

The author declares that he has no conflict of interest. This article does not contain any studies with human or animal subjects.

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